

Fabrication of self-ameliorating microphases between composite plies by inkjet printing

Y. Zhang^{1*}, P. J. Smith^{1*}, A. Hodzic^{1,3}, J. E. Stringer¹, T. Swait³, C. Soutis², R. Grainger³

¹ Department of Mechanical Engineering, The University of Sheffield, Sheffield, UK,

² Aerospace Research Institute, The University of Manchester, Manchester, UK,

³ Advanced Manufacturing Research Centre, The University of Sheffield, UK

*Corresponding authors (mep11yz@sheffield.ac.uk & patrick.smith@sheffield.ac.uk)

Keywords: *inkjet printing, self-ameliorating, carbon fibre composites*

1 Introduction

Inkjet printing has been extensively explored as a manufacturing technique over the last two decades due to its ability to precisely print pico-litre droplets according to predefined patterns without masks. It is an attractive method for many areas such as printed electronics [1] and tissue engineered scaffolds [2] on account of its minimum waste generation. The main consideration for using inkjet printing is in the physical and rheological properties of inks which are composed of either solutions or suspensions. Viscosity and surface tension are the most important factors which determine the printability of inks [3].

Composites are of increasing interest due to their light weight and relatively high mechanical properties such as tensile strength and flexural modulus. A reinforced fibre or other filler is embedded into the composite with the aim of improving their strength and stiffness-to-weight ratio [4]. However, the trade-off for this gain in mechanical strength is their poor performance under impact loading which leads to delamination. In order to extend the lifetime of this material, researchers began investigating self-repairing strategies; numerous self-healing materials with different healing mechanisms have been reported to date [5]. In this study, a new method is presented that uses inkjet printing to deposit, or fabricate, self-ameliorating agents between composite plies

prior to the curing cycle.

A research grade inkjet printer was used to place self-ameliorating agents onto the surfaces of carbon fibre reinforced epoxy pre-pregs. The interface between the plies is likely to be the main source of micro-cracks hence this strategic deposition imparts multifunctional properties whilst enhancing its structural integrity in service. The self-ameliorating agents took the form of standard polymers, which need to be classified as M15P and M20P at this stage (due to IP application which will be finalised in time for the conference). The addition of the agents contributed to improved properties in the interlaminar shear modulus and Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness (G_{Ic}).

2 Experimental

All samples were printed at room temperature using a JetLab 4xl printer from MicroFab. The substrate used was Cycom 977-2 pre-preg. Samples were subsequently cured using autoclave. The samples were “damaged” using a tensometer which is normally used for short beam shear testing; the applied load was stopped just after the maximum load displacement. The healing samples were heated at 177 °C for two hours, chosen as the harshest case scenario.

A hexagonal pattern was chosen for printing as

shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. The self-ameliorating agents were printed on CFRP pre-pregs in a hexagonal pattern.

3 Results and Discussion

The addition of self-ameliorating agents increased the stiffness, with samples containing M15P showing the best performance. Up to 33.84% increased stiffness compared to the virgin samples can be seen in Figure 2. Figure 3 shows that the addition of M15P has greatly increased mode I interlaminar fracture toughness (G_{Ic}) and that of M20P has delivered a slight increase. Although, the printing of M15P between composite plies has enhanced G_{Ic} , it is indicative that the addition of self-ameliorating agents by inkjet printing can assist in healing.

Fig. 2. Samples with the inkjet-printed addition of self-ameliorating agents (M20P & M15P) show increased stiffness compared to the virgin samples.

Fig. 3. Samples with the inkjet-printed addition of self-ameliorating agents (M20P & M15P) show higher G_{Ic} compared to the virgin samples, before and after self-healing process.

References

- [1] E. Tekin, P. J. Smith, S. Hoepfner, A. M. J. van der Berg, A. S. Susha, A. L. Rogach, J. Feldmann, and U. S. Schubert. "Inkjet printing of luminescent CdTe nanocrystal-polymer composites". *Advanced Functional Materials*, Vol. 17, pp 23-28, 2007.
- [2] M. J. Mondrinos, R. Dembzyński, L. Lu, V. K. C. Byrapogu, D. M. Wootton, P. I. Lelkes and J. Zhou. "Porogen-based solid freeform fabrication of polycaprolactone-calcium phosphate for tissue engineering". *Biomaterials*, Vol. 27, pp 4399-4408, 2006.
- [3] A. L. Dearden, P. J. Smith, D.Y. Shin, N. Reis, B. Derby and P. O'Brien. "A low curing temperature silver ink for use in ink-jet printing and subsequent production of conductive tracks". *Macromolecular Rapid Communications*, Vol. 26, pp 315-318, 2005.
- [4] J. Morton, E.W. Godwin. "Impact response of tough carbon fibre composites". *Composite Structure*, Vol. 13, pp 1-19, 1989.
- [5] R. P. Wool. "Self-healing materials: a review", *Soft Matter*, Vol. 4, pp 400-418, 2008.